

ON THE MOVING BOUNDARY METHODS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF CATAPHORETIC SPEED OF COLLOIDS. PART II.

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The suitability of the moving boundary method as developed by Mukherjee for the determination of cataphoretic speeds of concentrated colloids in which the electrical conductivity of the colloid particles is comparable with those of the intermicellar electrolytes has been discussed in the light of the electrolytic migration theory of Kohlrausch and Weber. This theory has been verified with mixtures of KCl and KIO_3 . The conditions necessary for reliable cataphoretic measurements have been experimentally secured with two ferric oxide and two aluminium oxide hydrosols and cataphoretic speeds generally reproducible within 2% have been obtained. The cataphoretic speeds of the same sols have been obtained by the transport apparatus of Engel and Pauli and the results are also reproducible within about 2%. The results of the moving boundary method have been found to agree with those of the transport method, almost within the range of experimental accuracy.

In the determination of the cataphoretic velocity by the method of moving boundaries a colloid is regarded as a mixture of electrolytes, the colloidal micelles being assumed to be large polyvalent ions. A boundary is formed between the colloid and electrolytic solution, a constant current is passed and the rate of migration of the boundary is observed.

Mukherjee (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A** 102, 103) developed a method by which the potential gradient at and behind the moving boundary can be measured across side-limbs fused with the main cataphoretic tube. He showed from direct measurements that unless the upper electrolyte is suitably chosen the moving boundary method is liable to give erroneous results.

Choice of the suitable upper electrolyte must rest on a knowledge of the type of colloid whose cataphoretic velocity is being measured. Three cases have got to be distinguished :

Case 1. The colloid contains an excess of dissolved electrolytes so that the contribution of the micelle ions to the conduction of current is very small.

Case 2. The conductivity of the micelle ions is comparable with those of the intermicellar electrolytes.

Case 3. The colloid contains very little dissolved electrolyte except the "gegenion."

In the case of colloids of the first kind, the upper electrolyte should have the same composition as that of the intermicellar electrolyte and should be equiconducting with the colloid. This case has been dealt with in Part I (Sen-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 483) where it has been shown that under proper conditions moving boundary and microscopic methods give identical results.

In the case of colloids of the second kind, it is not possible to determine without actual measurements the composition of the suitable upper liquid with which the colloid will move unchanged. This has got to be obtained by trial and Mukherjee's cataphoretic tube appears to be a very convenient apparatus for such measurements.

The theory of the moving boundary method for colloids of the second kind, which rests on the relation of Kohlrausch (*Ann. Physik.*, 1897, **62**, 209) and Weber (*Sitzungsber. Berlin Akad.*, 1897, 936) for constant ionic migration has been recently reviewed by several workers (Henry and Brittain, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, **29**, 798; Komagata, *Tokyo Electrotech. Lab. Japan*, 1933, No. 348; Hacker, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1935, **41**, 147). Of these the work of Hacker deserves a special attention. He used Mukherjee's cataphoretic tube and showed that the relation of Kohlrausch and Weber holds good for mixtures of electrolytes. He also found experimentally, in the case of a ferric oxide sol, the suitable upper electrolyte with which the colloid moves unchanged. He, however, did not compare his results with those obtained by other methods. This appears desirable.

The case of colloids of the third kind corresponds with the solution of a single electrolyte and is comparatively simple. Its study is also expected to give some useful information. This will be dealt with in future.

In the present communication the suitability of the moving boundary method for (i) mixtures of potassium chloride and potassium iodate, (ii) two ferric oxide hydrosols and (iii) two aluminium oxide hydrosols has been studied and the results have been compared with those obtained by the transport method as developed by Engel and Pauli (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, **126**, 247).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Moving Boundary Method.

FIG. 1.
Moving boundary apparatus.

Cataphoretic measurements have been carried out with a U-tube, in which two wide stop-cocks, having the same bore as that of the cataphoretic tube, have been fused in the body of the tube. The apparatus is shown in Fig. 1. This apparatus is specially suitable for colourless solutions.

The tube is filled with the colloid up to the stop-cocks I and II*. The stop-cocks are then closed and the top portion is filled with the suitable covering electrolyte, stop-cock III being kept open. The tube is then immersed in the thermostat, and stop-cock II is opened. After half an hour stop-cock I is opened and III closed. Current is allowed to flow in the proper direction and potential measurements taken at definite intervals between the side-tubes S_1 and S_2 . The measured potential remains at first constant, then rises as the boundary enters into the region between S_1 and S_2 and finally assumes a higher constant value as the boundary passes up the side tubes. The speed of the boundary, when it is between the side-tubes, is observed with a cathetometer and a stop-watch. Current is kept constant by means of a hand regulated rheostat.

The method of calculating the cataphoretic speed and specific conductivity behind the boundary has been detailed previously (Sen-Gupta, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 685).

Transport Method:

In the transport method the amount of colloid passing through any particular cross section of the solvent due to the passage of a definite quantity of electricity is analytically estimated. Besides the difficulties of analytical estimation the following two objections may be raised against the ordinary method**

(a) Electrodes being directly immersed in the colloid polarisation occurs. *e.g.*, in Paine's method (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 412) and,

(b) During electrolysis colloid in one region of the tube is diluted and in another region concentrated producing a corresponding mixing.

These two objections have been eliminated in the method of Ergel and Pauli (*loc. cit.*). Further, the analysis of unnecessarily large amount of colloids is avoided. The apparatus (Fig. 2) is really an extension of the moving boundary apparatus with this difference that the plane of

* The density of colloidal solutions is generally greater than that of the electrolytes which are adjusted with the colloids so that the electrolyte solutions are generally placed above the colloids.

** Mukherjee (*Kolloid Z.*, 1935, 72, 178) pointed out another source of error which sets a limit to the wide applicability of the transport method. This trouble comes in when the intermicellar electrolyte contains an excess of the ion present in the colloid and when the velocity of the ion is markedly different from that of the colloid.

FIG. 2.

Transport apparatus
(Engel and Pauli)

reference is placed well below the boundary and thus the troubles occurring at the boundary do not enter into the results. The apparatus of Engel and Pauli without any modification has been used in the present investigation. The working of the apparatus has been described by Engel and Pauli. The colloid is originally filled up to the stop-cocks I and II and after passing the current the amount of colloid in the region between III and IV is analysed. The cataphoretic speed is calculated by the formula

$$C.V. = \frac{(a/c - \phi)k_0}{i \cdot t}$$

where a is the amount of colloid in g. found in the region between stop-cocks III and IV, c , the concentration of the colloid in g. per c.c., ϕ , the volume in c.c. between stop-cocks I and III, k_0 , the specific conductivity of the colloid, i , the current strength and t , the time of electrolysis.

Equiconducting solutions of potassium chloride have generally been used as the upper electrolyte. The specific conductivity of the sol has been measured *in situ* by the conductivity electrodes EE' before and after passing the current. If the conductivities are different, this shows that the disturbances at the boundary have entered into the colloid down to the plane of reference. Such measurements are rejected.

Preparation of Sols.—Ferric oxide hydrosol A was prepared by the prolonged dialysis of a concentrated solution of FeCl_3 , partially neutralised with NH_4OH . The sol has been allowed to age for about one year.

Ferric oxide hydrosol B was prepared by the precipitation of hydrated Fe_2O_3 from a concentrated solution of FeCl_3 with NH_4OH . The precipitate was washed repeatedly with distilled water on a Buchner funnel and then peptised with the least amount of FeCl_3 . The resulting sol was dialysed for fifteen days with occasional change of distilled water and then allowed to age at 70° for twelve hours.

Aluminium oxide hydrosol A was prepared in the same way as ferric oxide hydrosol B and the sol allowed to age for one month at the room temperature.

Aluminium oxide hydrosol B was obtained by the electro dialysis of sol A in a three-chambered electro dialyser with occasional change of

water. With the progress of electro dialysis gelatinous precipitate was found to be thrown down. In order that the sol might not become too dilute, electro dialysis was stopped after three days. The sol was allowed to age for one month at the room temperature.

Analysis of the Sols.—Ferric oxide hydrosols were dissolved in hydrochloric acid and concentration of iron estimated by dichromate titration using diphenylamine.

Aluminium oxide hydrosols were also dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and concentration of aluminium estimated by the 8-oxyquinoline method (Berg, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 369).

Hydrogen Ion Concentration.— p_H has been measured with quinhydrone and glass electrodes McClatche (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2087) showed that the p_H of ferric oxide hydrosols could be estimated equally well by means of the quinhydrone and the glass electrodes, while hydrogen electrode gave erratic results. The same has also been observed in this investigation.

Chlorine Ion Concentration and Total Chlorine.—Chlorine ion concentration has been measured by means of silver-silver chloride electrodes, prepared by the method of Noyes and Ellis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 2534) and total chlorine estimated by means of volumetric titrations with standard solutions of silver nitrate after dissolving the colloid in nitric acid.

Both conductivity and p_H of freshly prepared sols have been found to change at first rapidly with time and finally become almost constant. The values of the conductivities and p_H of the sols have not measurably changed during the period of measurements.

Methods of measuring current strength, and potential gradient have been described previously (Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

R E S U L T S.

Composition. Compositions of the sols and of the ultrafiltrates are shown in Tables I and II. The ultrafiltrates of ferric oxide hydrosols contain negligible quantity of iron. Similar results have also been obtained recently by Kargin and Kiseleva* (*J. Phys. Chem. Russ.*, 1938, 11, 461).

The conductivity of the micelle ions can be calculated from the above tables assuming that the mobility of the electrolytic ions in the colloid and

* Absorption spectra of ferric oxide hydrosol was unaffected by the addition of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ or KCNS showing absence of any ferric ion.

TABLE I.

System.	Total iron as Fe_2O_3 .	p_H	Chlorine ion activity.	Total chlorine.	Specific condy. at 35° (mhos).
Ferric oxide hydrosol A	1.987%	3.37	$3.27 \times 10^{-3}N$	$43.6 \times 10^{-3}N$	$69.53 \times 10^{-}$
Ultrafiltrate of above	Negligible	3.09	...	1.24	52.30
Ferric oxide hydrosol B	1.471%	3.29	2.06	25.6	44.1
Ultrafiltrate of above	Negligible	3.09	...	0.95	27.3

TABLE II.

System.	Total aluminium as Al_2O_3 .	p_H	Chlorine ion activity.	Total chlorine.	Specific condy. at 35° (mhos)
Aluminium oxide hydrosol A.	1.271%	4.11	$2.30 \times 10^{-3}N$	$2.54 \times 10^{-3}N$	135.6×10^{-1}
Ultrafiltrate of above	0.0261	4.06	...	1.25×10^{-3}	64.02
Aluminium oxide hydrosol B.	0.654	5.10	3.3×10^{-4}	8.9×10^{-4}	4.28
Ultrafiltrate of above	0.0057	4.67	...	3.0×10^{-4}	3.81

in true solutions at same concentrations are equal. From the activities of Cl-ion and H-ion in Table I, the specific conductivity of ferric oxide hydrosol A due to the intermicellary electrolyte is

$$400 \times 4.3 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mho} + 90 \times 3.27 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mho} = 46.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mho.}$$

where 400 is the mobility of H-ion in a $10^{-4}N$ solution at 35° , 90, the same for Cl-ion at $10^{-3}N$ solution (Davis, "Conductivity of Solution," 2nd Ed. p. 205) and 4.3×10^{-7} and 3.27×10^{-6} are respectively the concentrations of H-ion and Cl-ion in g. equivalent per c. c. (see Table I). Thus the specific conductivity due to the micelle ion is 22.9×10^{-5} mho (69.5×10^{-5} mho $- 46.6 \times 10^{-5}$ mho). This can also be calculated in another way. The equivalent concentration of the micelle ion may be assumed to be given by the difference of a_{Cl} and a_{H} and equals $2.84 \times 10^{-3}N$. The mobility of the micelle ion (C. V. $\times F$) is about 57.6 (see Table XV) so that the specific conductivity due to the micelle ion equals 15.8×10^{-5} mho. In view of the simplifying assumptions involved in these calculations a close agreement between the two results is not

expected. It is, however, evident from the above that the specific conductivity of the micelle ions is comparable with that of the intermicellary electrolytes.

Reproducibility of Measurements.

The reproducibilities in the measurements of potentials and cataphoretic speeds are shown in Table III, IV and V.

Since the movement of the boundary has been generally followed over a length of 1 cm. and the boundary could be read to within 0.05 mm, a reproducibility of more than $\pm 0.5\%$ is not expected. The reproducibility is generally within 2% except in the case of aluminum oxide hydrosol A using KCl as the upper liquid. Equiconducting KCl solution is, however, not a suitable upper liquid for aluminium oxide hydrosols. The reproducibility is also not so good with aluminium oxide hydrosol B. In the measurement of specific conductivity of the sol behind the boundary the results are reproducible within 1%.

Measurement of Potential gradient in the Sol layer behind the Moving Boundary.

TABLE III.

Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. Fe_2O_3 sol A (sp. conductivity = 69.53×10^{-8} mho.)

Upper liquid HCl (sp. conductivity = 69.50×10^{-8} mho).

T = time in sec. P = potential in volts.

T	...	0	120	360	570	720	1080	1380	1860	2160	2280	2460	2700
P	...	2.937	2.909	2.906	2.906	2.962	3.425	3.897	4.651	5.02	5.085	5.122	5.1

Specific conductivity of the sol layer behind the boundary

$$= \frac{2.906}{5.122} \times 69.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mho} = 39.45 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mho.}$$

TABLE IV.

Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. Al_2O_3 sol A (sp. conductivity = 135.6×10^{-8} mho).

Upper liquid = equiconducting KCl.

Time (sec.)	...	0	480	840	1140	1440	1680	2040	2160	2280	2460
Potential (volt)	...	5.195	5.260	5.715	6.17	6.74	7.075	7.50	7.525	7.65	7.65

Sp. conductivity of the sol behind the boundary

$$= \frac{5.195}{7.650} \times 135.6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mho} = 92.1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mho} = 92.1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mho.}$$

Reproducibility of Cataphoretic Velocity Measurements.

TABLE V.

Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$

Fe ₂ O ₃ Hydrosol A (Sp. condy. = 69.53×10^{-5} mho). Upper liquid = Hydrochloric acid (Sp. condy. = 141.6×10^{-5} mho). Specific condy. of the sol behind the boundary = 57.24×10^{-5} mho.			Al ₂ O ₃ Hydrosol A (Sp. condy. = 135.6×10^{-5} mho). Upper liquid = AlCl ₃ solution (Sp. condy. = 137.2×10^{-5} mho). Sp. condy. behind the boundary = 136.0×10^{-5} mho.		
Time.	Distance.	C.V. (cm./sec.)	Time.	Distance.	C.V. cm./sec.
409 sec.	0.5 cm.	57.2×10^{-5}	211 sec.	0.3 cm.	59.7×10^{-5}
810	1.0	58.3	405	0.685	60.6
972	1.2	58.3	620	0.985	60.0

Mixed Electrolytes.

The results of the measurements with mixed electrolytes are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$. Upper electrolyte = 0.02N-KCl (sp conductivity = 33.12×10^{-4} mho).

Indicator composition.	Sp. condy. (mho).	Sp condy. behind the boundary from potential measurements. (mho).	V_{10_3} (cm./sec.)
0.02N-KIO ₃	24.6×10^{-4}	16.6×10^{-4} 16.3	43.2×10^{-5} 42.5
0.0133N-KIO ₃ 0.0067N-KCl	27.4	20.6 20.1	42.8 41.5
0.0067N-KIO ₃ 0.0133N-KCl	30.3	25.9 25.6	42.4 41.4

Velocity of iodate ion has been calculated by the relation,

$$V_{10_3} = \frac{V_{Cl} \cdot K_{KIO_3}}{K^1 K_0 / K - K_{KCl}}$$

where K , K_0 and K^1 denote respectively the specific conductivity of the indicator behind the boundary, of the original indicator solution, and of the KCl layer, and K_{KCl} and K_{KIO_3} , the partial conductivities of the two electrolytes in the mixture and V_{Cl} and V_{10_3} , the absolute velocities of Cl-ion and IO₃-ion respectively. V_{Cl} has been put equal to 86.3×10^{-5} cm/sec. at 35°

and at 0.02N concentration (Sen-Gupta and Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 645). Values for K_{KCl} and K_{KIO_3} have been obtained by dividing the equivalent conductivities at 0.02N strength by the corresponding concentration in the mixture. Since the ionic strength of the indicator has been kept constant at 0.02N, this gives the true partial conductivities of the electrolytes. Values for V_{IO_3} , thus obtained have been given in the fourth column of Table VI.

V_{IO_3} , calculated from the specific conductivity and the transport number at 0.02N concentration at 35° ($T_{IO_3} = 0.336$) and is found to be 42.8×10^{-5} cm/sec. The observed and calculated values for the velocity of iodate ion are in good agreement.

Ferric Oxide Hydrosol.

In Tables VII and VIII are given the results of measurements with ferric oxide hydrosols A and B. Hydrochloric acid of different concentrations has been used as the upper liquid. It follows from theoretical con-

TABLE VII.

Temp. 35° ± 0.05°.

Ferric oxide hydrosol A (Sp. condy. = 69.53×10^{-5} mho).			Ferric oxide hydrosol B (Sp. condy. = 44.1×10^{-5} mho).		
Specific conductivity of upper liquid (HCl) (mho).	Specific conductivity of sol following the boundary (mho).	C.V. (cm/sec.).	Specific conductivity of upper liquid (HCl) (mho).	Specific conductivity of sol following the boundary (mho).	C.V. (cm/sec.).
69.53 × 10 ⁻⁵	38.74 × 10 ⁻⁵	68.4 × 10 ⁻⁵ 69.5 66.3	48.28 × 10 ⁻⁵	25.54 × 10 ⁻⁵	64.6 × 10 ⁻⁵ 61.4
			48.28	25.37	61.1
69.53	39.45	66.7 66.8			62.6 64.4
141.6	57.24	57.2 58.3 58.3	78.92	33.63	60.9 60.3 60.5
163.1	64.22	57.7 57.6 57.2	114.3	39.20	54.9 56.2
			155.5	43.98	51.9
188.7	72.02	57.7 57.7 57.9			51.7
			155.5	43.83	51.7 52.0
			158.6	44.16	50.0 51.1
			168.7	47.00	50.8 52.1

* From potential measurements.

siderations that only rising boundaries should remain sharp. This has actually been found to be the case. The concentration of hydrochloric acid has been experimentally found for which the conductivity of the sol layer following the boundary is approximately the same as that of the original sol. This represents the ideal condition according to the relation of Kohirausch and Weber. The measured cataphoretic velocity at this region does not change with slight alteration in the specific conductivity of the upper liquid. The results also correspond with the values obtained by the transport method.

With ferric oxide hydrosol B moving boundary measurements have also been carried out with (a) ultrafiltrate and (b) mixtures of HCl and FeCl₃ solutions as the leading electrolyte. It has been found that the measured cataphoretic speeds change with the specific conductivities of the FeCl₃ and HCl mixtures.

TABLE VIII.

Temp. = 35° ± 0.05°.

Ferric oxide hydrosol B.

Upper electrolyte.	Specific conductivity of upper electrolyte. sol following the boundary.*		C.V. (cm/sec.).
Ultrafiltrate of the sol	27.26 × 10 ⁻⁵ (mho.)	22.16 × 10 ⁻⁵ (mho)	63.9 × 10 ⁻⁴ 66.4
Mixture of FeCl ₃ and HCl <i>p_H</i> = 3.21	45.0	30.18	63.7 63.9
Mixture of FeCl ₃ and HCl <i>p_H</i> = 3.15	97.12	48.45	56.6 57.1
Mixture of FeCl ₃ and HCl <i>p_H</i> = 3.14	143.8	56.5	46.8 47.2

* From potential measurements.

Aluminium Oxide Hydrosol.

In Table IX results of measurements with aluminium oxide hydrosols A and B have been recorded.

Aluminium oxide hydrosol A has a specific conductivity of 135.6 × 10⁻⁵ mho. An equiconducting solution of AlCl₃ has the same *p_H* as that of the sol namely 4.11. Further the cataphoretic speed of the particles is nearly the same as that of Al ion in the equiconducting solution. These con-

siderations show that the equiconducting AlCl_3 solution should serve the purpose of the upper electrolyte. Measurements have been carried out with an equiconducting KCl solution for comparison. The specific conductivity of the sol behind the boundary is much less in the latter case and the observed cataphoretic speeds are also lower.

With aluminium oxide hydrosol B different solutions of AlCl_3 have been tried until one is found for which the specific conductivity of the sol behind the boundary is the same as that of the original sol. Both the rising and falling boundaries remained sharp in this case. Theoretical considerations, however, show that only rising boundaries give the true cataphoretic speeds.

TABLE IX.

Temp. $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Al_2O_3 Hydrosol A (sp. condy. 1.35×10^{-5} mho).			Al_2O_3 Hydrosol B (sp. condy. $= 4.28 \times 10^{-5}$ mho).			
Specific conductivity of upper electrolyte (mho).	sol following the boundary* (mho).	C V. (cm/sec.)	Specific conductivity of upper electrolyte (mho). (AlCl_3) ₁	sol following the boundary.* (mho).	C V. (cm/sec.) Falling boundary.	Rising boundary.
KCl— 1.35×10^{-5}	90.6×10^{-5}	54.6×10^{-5}	4.28×10^{-5}	3.71×10^{-5}	49.5×10^{-5}	—
		52.5			49.2	
		55.7			46.9	
KCl— 1.35×10^{-5}	101.3	53.7	4.36	3.71	45.1	53.5×10^{-5}
		52.8			44.1	54.6
		54.3	5.00	4.26	44.6	50.8
AlCl_3 — 1.37×10^{-5}	136.0	59.7	5.50	4.51	47.3	54.1
		60.7			47.3	55.0
		60.0			43.9	53.8

* From potential measurements.

Transport Method.

The apparatus was calibrated with $0.1N\text{-KIO}_3$. The results of three independent measurements are shown in Table X.

TABLE X.

Temp. $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$.

$M/10\text{-KIO}_3$ soln. Upper electrolyte = $M/10\text{-KCl}$ soln. $\phi = 5.602$ c.c.

Time of passing the current.	Current (amp).	KIO_3 soln. transported	T_{10_3}
3600 sec.	10.74×10^{-3}	1.33 c.c.	0.332
3600	13.02	1.60	0.330
3420	13.50	1.58	0.330

Transport number of IO_3 -ion in KIO_3 at 35° and at the dilution $0.1N$ can be calculated from the mobility data at 18° and from the transport number equation of Onsager and comes out to be 0.326 .

The results of measurements with ferric oxide hydrosol A and B and aluminium oxide hydrosol A and B are shown in Tables XI—XIV. The results in the transport method are independent of the specific conductivity of the upper electrolyte as has been shown with ferric oxide hydrosol B.

TABLE XI

Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$ Ferric oxide hydrosol A (sp. condy. = 69.53×10^{-5} mho).
Upper electrolyte = KCl (sp. condy. = 69.50×10^{-5} mho.).

Time of passing the current.	Current (amp.).	Sol. transported.	C.V. (cm/sec.)
2700 sec.	49.7×10^{-8}	1.07 c.c.	55.5×10^{-8}
2400	57.7	1.146	57.4

TABLE XII.

Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. Ferric oxide hydrosol B (sp. condy. = 44.1×10^{-5} mho).
Upper liquid = HCl.

Sp. condy of upper electrolyte in mho.	Time of passing the current.	Current in amp.	Sol transported.	C.V. (cm/sec.)
60.16×10^{-5}	2400 sec.	50.57×10^{-8}	1.441 c.c.	52.3×10^{-8}
78.92	2400	60.10	1.688	51.5
73.4	2400	54.94	1.537	51.3

TABLE XIII.

Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. Aluminium oxide hydrosol A (sp. condy. = 135.6×10^{-5} mho). Upper electrolyte = KCl solution (sp. condy. = 135.4×10^{-5} mho).

Time of passing the current.	Current (amp.).	Sol transported.	C.V. (cm/sec.)
3600 sec.	91.27×10^{-8}	1.41 c.c.	58.1×10^{-8}
3600	121.4	1.83	57.7

TABLE XIV.

Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$. Aluminium oxide hydrosol B (sp. condy = 4.28×10^{-5} mho). Upper electrolyte = KCl (sp. condy.) 4.26×10^{-5} mho).

Time of passing the current.	Current (amp.).	Sol transported.	C.V. (cm/sec.).
2700 sec.	36.0×10^{-8}	1.152 c.c.	50.4×10^{-6}
2700	41.4	1.319	50.5

The results of measurements by the transport method have been compared with those obtained by the moving boundary method in Table XV. The agreement is very close and generally within the range of experimental accuracy.

TABLE XV.

Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$.

Sol.	C.V. (cm/sec.) obtained by	
	moving boundary method.	transport method.
Fe ₂ O ₃ Sol A	57.6×10^{-5}	56.5×10^{-5}
Fe ₂ O ₃ Sol B	51.4	51.7
Al ₂ O ₃ Sol A	60.1	57.9
Al ₂ O ₃ Sol B	52.5	50.4

CONCLUSION.

The results indicate that for concentrated colloids the moving boundary method is as suitable as the transport method. The suitability of the moving boundary method, however, depends on the direct determination of the potential gradient of the sol layer behind the boundary besides the rate of migration of the latter. If one tries to calculate the cataphoretic speed from the specific conductivity of the leading electrolyte the result becomes two to three times greater.

In the procedure of Kruyt and Willigen (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 22) the cataphoretic speed with the rising boundary is calculated from the speed of the boundary and the potential gradient in the upper electrolyte (ultrafiltrate) and the cataphoretic speed with the falling boundary from the speed of the boundary and the potential gradient in the sol layer. The mean of the two is assumed to represent the true cataphoretic speed,

With concentrated colloids, however, it is not generally possible to get both the boundaries sharp.

Thus it may be stated that an accurate determination of the cataphoretic speed of concentrated colloids rests on (a) the proper choice of the upper electrolyte and (b) the direct determination of the potential gradient or specific conductivity of the indicator solution behind the boundary.

The transport method is comparatively free from such troubles. If, however, the intermicellary electrolyte contains an excess of the ion present in the colloid (e g. Al-ion in aluminium oxide hydrosol) and if the mobility of the ion is markedly different from that of the colloid then the transport method becomes unsuitable. In the present investigation with the aluminium oxide hydrosols the concentration of Al-ion : total Al in the colloid was less than 1 : 50 as estimated by means of ultrafiltration. Further, the mobility of Al-ion is almost the same as that of the colloid. Thus the error introduced due to the presence of Al-ion is negligible.

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